

Primes and Amazing Shapes from Pi Digits

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Pi is the ratio of the circumference of a circle to its diameter. It is known to be irrational and its decimal expansion therefore does not terminate or repeat. The number of digits in pi grows indefinitely. Though digits of pi have been studied extensively including locating primes of different kinds in pi digits but in this paper, you will find two new areas of pi digit applications i.e. piorial primes from product of pi digits and amazing shapes using pi digits. Interestingly the digits of pi can be represented in many amazing shapes like triangle, rhombus, hexagonal, etc but for this, it is necessary that number of digits in pi must be so selected, that can represent that shape. In this paper you will find as to how amazing shapes can be made using pi digits.

Let π_n denotes the n^{th} digit in the decimal expansion of π . The piorial can be defined as the product of first n digits in the decimal expansion of π and can be denoted by $\pi_n\$$. So,

$$\pi_1\$ = 3$$

$$\pi_2\$ = 3 \times 1 = 3$$

$$\pi_3\$ = 3 \times 1 \times 4 = 12$$

$$\pi_4 = 3 \times 1 \times 4 \times 1 = 12$$

$$\pi_5 = 3 \times 1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 5 = 60 \text{ and so on.}$$

This is analog of factorial as piorial is product of digits of pi and factorial is product of natural numbers. The values of π_n for $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, \dots$, are 3, 3, 12, 12, 60, 540, 1080,

It is interesting to note that $\pi_n = 0$ for $n > 32$, because the 33rd digit in the decimal expansion of pi is zero (First 32 digits of decimal expansion of π does not contain the digit zero). So the largest value of π_n is obtained by multiplying first 32 digits of π and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{32} &= 3 \times 1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 5 \times 9 \times 2 \times 6 \times 5 \times 3 \times 5 \times 8 \times 9 \times 7 \times 9 \times 3 \times 2 \times 3 \times 8 \times 4 \times 6 \times 2 \times 6 \times 4 \times 3 \times 3 \times 8 \times 3 \times 2 \times 7 \times 9 \times 5 \\ &= 49764378767523840000 \end{aligned}$$

Piorial Primes :

Similar to factorial primes, a piorial prime can be defined as a prime number that is one less or one more than a piorial i.e. of the form $\pi_n \pm 1$, where π_n is a piorial. All piorial prime of both the forms are given below.

Piorial prime of the form $\pi_n - 1$ are given by $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 12, 14, 15$ and 16. The corresponding piorial primes are 2, 2, 11, 11, 59, 3887999, 244943999, 2204495999 and 6613487999.

Piorial prime of the form $\pi_n + 1$ are given by $n = 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 19$ and 32. The corresponding piorial primes are 13, 13, 61, 541, 6481, 32401, 317447424001 and 49764378767523840001.

Piorial and piorial primes can be generalized to include product of successive digits in pi not only from first digit but from anywhere in the digit sequence of π . Let the generalized piorial be denoted by π_{n_1, n_2} , where, product of digits is to be taken from position n_1 to position n_2 , in the decimal expansion of pi. Note that piorial π_n is a special case of π_{n_1, n_2} , where $n_1 = 1$ (omitted) and $n_2 = n$. Similarly piorial primes will be of the form $\pi_{n_1, n_2} \pm 1$.

The position of successive locations of zeros in decimal expansion of first one thousand digits of π is : 33, 51, 55, 66, 72, 78, 86, 98, 107, 117, 122, 129, 133, 147, 160, 165, 168, 177, 196, 208, 246, 249, 265, 271, 288, 292, 308, 309, 312, 328, 331, 341, 358, 361, 362, 367, 370, 376, 399, 404, 409, 422, 444, 452, 494, 514, 521, 524, 544, 546, 553, 558, 562, 597, 602, 603, 604, 619, 639, 658, 660, 670, 683, 685, 704, 716, 721, 725, 747, 751, 756, 776, 782, 794, 803, 816, 819, 828, 839, 854, 856, 857, 858, 879, 886, 900, 910, 958, 969, 974, 975, 990, 997.

This gives the group of successive non-zero digits of pi. For example the position of digit zero is 33 and then 51 in the decimal expansion of pi, so all digits from position 34 to position 50 are non-zero.

Hence

$$\pi_{34, 50}\$ = 2 \times 8 \times 8 \times 4 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7 \times 1 \times 6 \times 9 \times 3 \times 9 \times 9 \times 3 \times 7 \times 5 \times 1 = 44442639360$$

Similarly we can find piorials for other positions of non-zero digits. For example,

$$\pi_{52, 54}\$ = 5 \times 8 \times 2 = 80$$

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{209, 245}\$ &= 9 \times 7 \times 5 \times 6 \times 6 \times 5 \times 9 \times 3 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4 \times 6 \times 1 \times 2 \times 8 \times 4 \times 7 \times 5 \times 6 \times 4 \times 8 \times 2 \times 3 \times 3 \times 7 \times \\ &\quad 8 \times 6 \times 7 \times 8 \times 3 \times 1 \times 6 \times 5 \times 2 \times 7 \times 1 \times 2 \\ &= 161841132252545679360000 \end{aligned}$$

Among the first 10 million digits of pi, largest sequence of non-zero digits (i.e. 129 digits) starts at position 5527033 and ends at 5527161, so

$$\pi_{5527033, 5527161}\$ =$$

$$\begin{aligned} &8 \times 7 \times 5 \times 4 \times 4 \times 7 \times 1 \times 9 \times 4 \times 6 \times 5 \times 2 \times 7 \times 4 \times 7 \times 9 \times 6 \times 8 \times 1 \times 3 \times 2 \times 8 \times 5 \times 1 \times 8 \times 6 \times 4 \times 8 \times 5 \times 1 \times 7 \times 4 \times 7 \times \\ &5 \times 9 \times 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 4 \times 6 \times 2 \times 6 \times 1 \times 7 \times 1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 2 \times 6 \times 3 \times 2 \times 8 \times 3 \times 5 \times 6 \times 9 \times 7 \times 6 \times 3 \times 3 \times 6 \times 6 \times \\ &5 \times 4 \times 2 \times 8 \times 8 \times 7 \times 5 \times 9 \times 2 \times 3 \times 7 \times 7 \times 6 \times 9 \times 4 \times 9 \times 9 \times 2 \times 3 \times 9 \times 3 \times 3 \times 7 \times 2 \times 8 \times 4 \times 8 \times 3 \times 5 \times 8 \times \\ &6 \times 8 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 5 \times 7 \times 4 \times 7 \times 9 \times 3 \times 8 \times 9 \times 2 \times 4 \times 9 \times 6 \times 5 \times 9 \times 7 \times 9 \times 7 \times 3 \times 7 \times 4 \times 7 \times 4 \times 6 \times 5 \times 7 \times \\ &2 \times 5 \times 3 \times 4 \times 6 \times 5 \times 6 = \\ &14954698506464644801573447081805717579392800396899622828572056 \\ &591584460800000000000000 \end{aligned}$$

The piorial primes for this group of non-zero digits of π are given below:

Piorial prime of the form $\pi_{5527033, 5527161} \$ -1$ are 7, 282239, 474163199, 1896652799, 296005728856965119999, 1385849316866983138753555090127192063999999999, 858242688417740440636043067630338653586227793158471679999999999, 756970051184447068640989985649958692463052913565772021759999999999 and 3178547523725540619106262589343602548000057706179219350251110399999999999.

Piorial prime of the form $\pi_{5527033, 5527161} \$ +1$ are 281, 4881, 282241, 1896652801, 13276569601, 34412868403201, 134268198609519378432000001 and 841077834649385631823322206277731880514503237295302246400000000001

It will be an interesting exercise to look for larger and larger piorial primes in the decimal expansion of π .

Amazing shapes from Pi digits :

For any shape to be represented by digits in the decimal expansion of pi, it is necessary that number of digits chosen must be such, which can represent that shape. Using pi digits, it is possible to draw various shapes like triangle, rhombus, hexagonal, octagonal, etc. For geometrical shapes like triangle, rhombus, hexagonal, octagonal, two sides are considered equal, if number of digits placed on each side is equal. So, for equilateral triangle, the number of digits of each of the three sides must be equal. The first 500 digits of pi can be seen below:

3.14159265358979323846264338327950288419716939937510582097494459
230781640628620899862803482534211706798214808651328230664709384460
955058223172535940812848111745028410270193852110555964462294895
49303819644288109756659334461284756482337867831652712019091456485
6692346034861045432664821339360726024914127372458700660631558817
488152092096282925409171536436789259036001133053054882046652138
4146951941511609433057270365759591953092186117381932611793105118
5480744623799627495673518857527248912279381830119491

Equilateral triangle from Pi digits :

It can be seen from figure 1 that 1st row consists of 1 digit, 2nd row consists of 2 digits, 3rd row consists of 3 digits and so on. So, n^{th} row consists of n digits. So the number of digits in any triangle is the partial sum of series $1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + \dots + n$, which is always a triangular number T_n given by $n \times (n+1)/2$. So if number of digits in decimal expansion of pi equals a triangular number then those digits of pi can be represented in the form of triangles as shown in figure 1. It can be seen that this triangular shape is actually an equilateral triangle that has all three sides of equal length (i.e. equal number of digits).

Figure 1 : Equilateral triangle from First T_n digits of pi

Rhombus from Pi digits :

It can be seen from figure 2 that rhombus can be represented as combination of two triangles, one with $n \times (n+1)/2$ digits placed upside down below the base of

other triangle with $(n+1) \times (n+2)/2$ digits. Since sum of two consecutive triangular numbers is always a perfect square, so if number of digits in decimal expansion of pi equals a perfect square, then those digits of pi can be represented in the form of rhombus as shown in figure 2. It can be seen that this rhombus shape has all four sides of equal length (i.e. equal number of digits) and two unequal diagonals.

Figure 2 : Rhombus from First n^2 digits of pi

Hexagon from Pi digits :

It can be seen from figure 3 that first row consists of d digit (where d is the number of digits on each side), each subsequent row consists of 2 digits more than the previous row till we reach d^{th} row. After d^{th} row, each subsequent row consists of 2 digits less than the previous row till we reach the last row that is $(2d-1)^{\text{th}}$ row. So the number of digits in any such hexagonal shape is $4 \times d \times d - 5 \times d + 2$. So if number of digits in decimal expansion of pi equals to $4 \times d \times d - 5 \times d + 2$, then those digits of pi can be represented in the form of hexagon as shown in figure 3. It shall be noted that each side of the hexagon consists of d digits.

Figure 3 : Hexagon from First $4d^2 - 5d + 2$ digits of pi

Octagon from factorial digits :

If d is the number of digits on each side and number of digits in decimal expansion of pi equals to $7 \times d \times d - 10 \times d + 4$, then those digits of pi can be represented

in the form of octagon as shown in figure 4. It shall be noted that each side of the octagon consists of d digits.

Figure 4 : Octagon from First $7d^2 - 10d + 4$ digits of pi

Isosceles Triangle from Pi digits :

It can be seen from figure 5 that 1st row consists of 1 digit, 2nd row consists of 3 digits, 3rd row consists of 5 digits and so on. So, n^{th} row consists of $(2n-1)$ digits. So the number of digits is the partial sum of series $1+3+5+7+9+\dots$ which is always a perfect square. So if number of digits in decimal expansion of pi equals is perfect

square, then those digits of pi can be represented in the form of Isosceles Triangle as shown in figure 5. It can be seen that shape is actually an isosceles triangle that has two sides of equal length.

Figure 5 : Isosceles Triangle from First n^2 digits of pi

Using pi digits, it is possible to draw alphabetical shapes like E, F, I, L, T, etc. It will be an interesting past time to attempt to draw the above mentioned shapes.

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